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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Angel in Red Vest

I knew it was a calling
to serve while wearing the red vest.
Not just a uniform,
but a promise
to stand with the community.

In every fieldwork, I found fulfillment,
because I knew
a life had been touched,
a voice had been heard,
a burden had been shared.

Working for the people
has always been meaningful.
I met individuals who inspired me
to grow and do better in my craft.
I met mentors who taught me with patience,
guides who walked beside me
throughout my journey
as an angel in a red vest.

Wearing it,
I reached places I never imagined
roads unfamiliar,
communities once distant.
The red vest pushed me forward:
to help,
to guide,
to protect
the marginalized.

I met people living in poverty,
yet holding on to hope.
I met those who lived alone,
yet found family in their community.
I stood among people in times of disaster,
where *bayanihan* lives on
unbroken, unwavering.

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No matter how far the journey,
the red vest always found its way
to those in need.

And in those moments,
I realized
this was more than service.
It was purpose.
It was humanity in action.

This red vest made me proud
of my profession.
It opened my eyes
to the bigger picture
of struggle,
of resilience,
of community.

I may not wear it now,
but the lessons it gave me
are stitched into who I am.
The experiences remain,
guiding me still.

With pride and honor,
I once wore the red vest.